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Separation Workflow

Overall study design

Title of the study				Benchmarking Lipid Quantitation from Skin Swab Sebum-Rich Samples to Establish Mass Spectrometry-Based Diagnostic Methodology			
Document creation date		06/26/2026		Principal investigator		Perdita Barran	
Institution		Manchester Institute of Biotechnology		Corresponding Email		perdita.barran@manchester.ac.uk	
Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?		Targeted		Clinical		Yes	

Lipid extraction

Extraction method		1-phase system		pH adjustment		None	
1-phase system		Methanol		Derivatization		NA	
Were internal standards added prior extraction?		No					

Analytical platform

Ionization additives		Ammonium formate, Formic acid		Number of separation dimensions		One dimension	
Separation type 1		LC		Separation mode 1 (liquid)		RP	
Detector		Mass spectrometer		MS type		QQQ	
MS vendor		Waters		Ion source		ESI	
MS Level		MS ¹ , MS ²		Mass resolution for detected ion at MS ¹		Low resolution	
Resolution at MS ¹		Low		Recording mode of raw data at MS ¹		Profile mode	
Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)		1		Mass resolution for detected ion at MS ²		Low resolution	
Resolution at MS ²		Low		Recording mode of raw data at MS ²		Profile mode	
Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used		No					

Quality control

Blanks		Yes		Type of Blanks		Extraction blank, Solvent blank	
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Quality control	Yes	Type of QC sample	Sample pool
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Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Lipid recovery	Yes
Dynamic quantification range	Yes	Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	Yes
Precision	No	Accuracy	No
Guidelines followed	FDA		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Yes	Link to repository / ID to entry	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/MTBLS13311
Are metadata available?	Yes	Summary data	Quantification data
Raw data upload	Yes		

Sample Descriptions

Nose2Diagnose / Human / Other liquid material

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Temperature handling original sample	Room temperature
Instant sample preparation	No	Storage temperature	-80 °C
Additives	None		

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	TG	MS Level for identification	MS ¹
Identification level	Species level	MS ¹ adduct	[M+NH4] ⁺
Isotope correction at MS ¹	No	MS ¹ verified by standard	No
Background check at MS ¹	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	S/N ratio > 3	RT verified by standard	No
Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No	Model for separation prediction	No
Lipid Identification Software	Homemade	Data manipulation	Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes		

1) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ¹ , MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
15:0-18:1-d7-15:0-TG	523.5	for all TGs with one double bond	

15:0-18:1-d7-15:0-TG	570.5	for all TGs with one double bond
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Internal lipid standard(s) MS¹

Internal standard	Endogenous subclass
15:0-18:1-d7-15:0-TG	for all TGs with one double bond

Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	No
Type I isotope correction	No	Limit of quantification	S/N ratio > 10
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	Skyline
Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC		